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CHANGING BELIEFS ABOUT INTELLIGENCE BY CHANGING THE WAY MATHEMATICS QUESTIONS ARE POSED

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ABSTRACT

The social psychology theory of growth mindsets – the belief that academic ability is not fixed at birth but can be developed – explains why students may fail to do what they know they should to succeed academically. Lasting behaviour change requires a change in the beliefs that underpin the behaviour.

Recent evidence suggests that developing growth mindsets in engineering students may be more successful if interventions focus on changing learning environments and not just changing students. Following this direction, the aim of this work-in-progress paper is to describe a design-based research framework to design and evaluate modifications to tasks and communication in engineering mathematics courses to support the development of growth mindsets over multiple semesters.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Student dropout from engineering studies continues to be an issue of global concern, motivating much engineering education research. In countries where entry to engineering programmes is highly competitive, it is puzzling that many engineering students who were high academic achievers in school fail at university. Amongst other things, academic success requires appropriate academic behaviour, such as reviewing errors made in tests and not giving up easily when work is challenging. Failing an assessment is an indication that a change in behaviour is necessary. However, realising that one's behaviour should change is often not enough to cause a lasting change in behaviour. Social psychology theories propose that behaviour change requires a change in the beliefs that underpin the behaviour. Specifically, the theory of 'growth mindsets' [1] – the belief that your academic ability is not inherent but can always be further developed – explains why students may know what behaviour they should change (for example asking questions when stuck) but still not make the behaviour change and be at greater risk of dropout.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Mindset and academic success

Holding a growth mindset means believing that your academic ability is not a biological trait beyond your control but can be increased through appropriate effort [1]. Compared to students who hold fixed mindsets, students with growth mindsets are more likely to be intrinsically motivated to learn and they are more likely to use effective study practices. Students with fixed mindsets are more likely to resist study behaviour that would mark them as a 'hard worker' and to set unobtainable, perfectionist goals which can lead to anxiety and depression [2].

Mindset theory [1] has been shown to impact students' behaviour and academic success [3]. Two meta-analyses of the effect of growth mindset interventions on academic achievement [4] showed that there is in general a small positive effect on achievement for students with a growth mindset. Importantly for institutions that value supporting diverse student populations, achievement gains were greatest for students from low-socio-economic backgrounds. However, a systematic literature review on developing growth mindsets in engineering students [5] showed that it is not yet clear how to develop growth mindsets. It would seem that growth mindsets are more likely to be developed in an environment that reinforces growth mindset messages.

2.2 Implications of mindset theory for educators

Growth mindsets and fixed mindsets can be promoted through teaching practices based on different learning theories [6]. Misinterpretation of mindset theory can lead to blaming students for not holding the right kind of mindset rather than recognising the systemic ways that a fixed mindset may be reinforced. Recent evidence suggests that growth mindsets may be developed through course structures such as using active learning, re-taking assessments, and showing students why the

selected topics are relevant to them [7]. Furthermore, posing mathematics questions based on growth-mindset-promoting principles [8] instead of in a traditional way were found to increase students' motivation to work on problems [7].

Boaler's [8] growth mindset principles for course design address the increasing diversity in high school backgrounds of engineering students. The principles include:

- Using 'low floor, high ceiling' activities to keep all students engaged.
- Using multiple methods, pathways, and representations.
- Asking the problem before teaching the method to solve it.
- Asking students to explain mathematics using a visual representation.
- Giving students opportunities to conduct their own inquiries.
- Asking students to reason out and convince someone of their findings.

3 RATIONALE AND RESEARCH QUESTION

This research will contribute to research on developing growth mindsets in engineering students in the context of engineering mathematics courses in South African universities. The aim of this work-in-progress paper is to describe a design-based research framework to identify, evaluate and design modifications to tasks and communication in engineering mathematics courses that support the development of growth mindsets in students and staff over multiple semesters.

4 METHODOLOGY

4.1 Design-based research

The five features of design-based research outlined in [9] matched the goals of this research project. First, the central goal of engineering mathematics courses is to equip students with confidence, knowledge and skills that they can use beyond their mathematics courses. The theory of growth mindsets is intertwined with this central goal as fixed mindsets work against the perseverance, self-reflection and collaboration needed in and beyond mathematics courses.

Second, developments and research on how tasks and communication in mathematics courses may reinforce fixed or growth mindsets are planned to take place through cycles of preparation (or more broadly 'design'[9]), action, analysis, and redesign over multiple semesters.

Third, the findings from this research will lead towards sharable theories on the choice of tasks and communication in engineering mathematics courses with implications for designers and educators.

Fourth, by researching current engineering mathematics courses in a variety of authentic settings (small and large classes, first- and second-year courses, different institutions), results will document successes and failures that lead to improvements, or that suggest revision of the theory. Results will refine understanding of mindset theory applied to engineering mathematics.

Fifth, text analysis methods based on mindset theories [7, 8], together with reflective collaboration between researchers and sharing findings in presentations and

publications will result in outcomes of interest to the engineering education community.

4.2 Phases

The research will use a design-based research framework with cycles of preparation/design, action and reflection. The research will follow the design-based research phases described in [10]:

PHASE 1: Analysis of practical problems by researchers and practitioners in collaboration

This phase marks the start of the first design-based research cycle focussing on preparation and design. The aim is to establish a community of collaborators (engineering mathematics lecturers) and collaboratively analyse existing course features to determine the extent to which growth mindsets are or are not being supported in tasks and communication, according to [8] and [1].

Surveys and interviews will be used to assess mindsets of students and staff in each of at least three semesters before and after changes are implemented, although challenges with assessing mindsets [5] are noted.

PHASE 2: Development of solutions informed by existing design principles

Using the growth mindsets principles [8], revisions to existing tasks and communication will be collaboratively developed by the researchers, for example, allowing students to choose to work on basic or more advanced questions and using peer-review to showcase alternative methods.

PHASE 3: Iterative cycles of testing and refinement of solutions in practice

Revised tasks and communication will be implemented in at least three semesters. Reflections informed by mindset assessment through surveys and interviews will contribute to the development of principles for enhancing the implementation of changes to tasks and assessments so that they encourage growth mindsets and discourage fixed mindsets.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The scope of the proposed research is the development of growth mindsets but the ultimate goal is improved student success. Other evaluative research may be needed to assess this research, for example the impact of participation in this project on broader issues, such as student wellbeing or the changes in the teaching practice of collaborators.

6 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

[Removed for blind review.]

REFERENCES

- [1] Dweck, C. (2006), *Mindset: The New Psychology of Success*, Random House Publishing Group, New York.

- [2] Schroeder, H. S., Dawood, S., Yalch, M. M., Donnellan, M. B. and Moser, J. S. (2015), The role of implicit theories in mental health symptoms, emotion regulation, and hypothetical treatment choices in college students, *Cognitive Therapy and Research*, Vol. 39, No. 2, pp. 120-139.
- [3] Broda, M., Yun, J., Schneider, B., Yeager, D.S., Walton, G.M. and Diemer, M. (2018), Reducing inequality in academic success for incoming college students: A randomized trial of growth mindset and belonging interventions, *Journal of Research on Educational Effectiveness*, Vol. 11, No. 3, pp. 317-338.
- [4] Sisk, V. F., Burgoyne, A. P., Sun, J., Butler, J. L. and Macnamara, B. N. (2018), To what extent and under which circumstances are growth mind-sets important to academic achievement? Two meta-analyses, *Psychological Science*, Vol. 29, No. 4, pp. 549-571.
- [5] Removed for blind review.
- [6] Removed for blind review.
- [7] Daly, I., Bourgaize, J. and Vernitski, A. (2019), Mathematical mindsets increase student motivation: Evidence from the EEG. *Trends in Neuroscience and Education*, Vol. 15, pp. 18-28.
- [8] Boaler, J. (2016), Designing mathematics classes to promote equity and engagement, *The Journal of Mathematical Behavior*, Vol. 100, No. 41, pp. 172-178, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmathb.2015.01.002>.
- [9] Carstensen, A. K. and Bernhard, J. (2019), Design science research—a powerful tool for improving methods in engineering education research, *European Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol. 44, No. 1-2, pp. 85-102.
- [10] Reeves, T. C. (2006), Design research from a technology perspective. In J. van den Akker, K. Gravemeijer, S. McKenney and N. Nieveen (Eds.), *Educational design research*, Routledge, London, pp. 52-66.